

Nowcasting Monthly Macroeconomic Variables in India Using Google Trends: A Machine Learning Approach

ABSTRACT

Timely assessment of macroeconomic conditions is particularly challenging in emerging economies like India, where official statistics are released with significant delays and frequent revisions. This study examines whether high-frequency digital trace data from Google Trends can enhance the nowcasting of four key Indian macroeconomic indicators: unemployment, consumer price index (CPI), real GDP, and GDP growth. Adopting the two-step approach of Woloszko (2020), we combine Google Trends with machine learning models to evaluate their predictive content. Results show that predictive performance is indicator-specific: unemployment is best captured by Lasso regression, CPI by decision trees, and real GDP and GDP growth by gradient boosting. Stock-like variables (real GDP and unemployment) exhibit strong alignment with official series, while flow measures such as GDP growth and CPI are more difficult to track, reflecting their inherent volatility. SHAP analysis further reveals that search intensity proxies for meaningful economic drivers, ranging from trade activity to consumer sentiment, and the framework successfully captures turning points during episodes such as the 2008 global financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first systematic application of Google Trends with machine learning to nowcast multiple macroeconomic indicators for India. The findings highlight the value of search-based behavioral data as a complementary, real-time source for economic monitoring, with important implications for policymakers and forecasters in data-scarce, rapidly evolving environments.

Keywords: Nowcast, Machine Learning, Macroeconomic variables, Google Trends Data, Correlation, Regression, Shapley Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Indian policymaking relies heavily on macroeconomic indicators. However, two key challenges limit their effectiveness. First, there is a significant publication lag: CPI data is released around 12 days after the reference month, unemployment data has a delay of about 45 days, and Real GDP and GDP growth rate figures are published roughly two months after the end of the quarter (CMIE, 2022; Ghate et.al, 2013). Second, we do not get these values at monthly frequency. Only CPI and unemployment figures are available monthly, while Real GDP and GDP growth are published quarterly.

In order to bridge this gap of delay in the publication of official data and frequency with which they are released, we need to estimate monthly data based on other available data. One way is to use survey data, but that has been challenged by studies such as Vermeulen (2012). According to this study, the underlying relationship between survey-based indicators and macroeconomic variables becomes unreliable when changes in economic activity are abrupt

and massive. They are also associated with substantial cost and resource implications, along with certain conceptual and operational challenges in terms of sample representativeness, estimation techniques (Bai et.al, 2016).

An alternative approach is to leverage high-frequency datasets, such as flight departures, satellite nighttime lights data, mobility reports based on anonymized personal data from Google and Apple, air quality indices, electricity consumption, credit card transactions, restaurant bookings, news-based indicators, etc. These alternative data sources have been increasingly used to proxy for economic activity (Henderson et.al, 2012; Chen et.al, 2019; Chetty et.al, 2020). In this study, we have used one such high-frequency dataset “Google Trends” generated through the volume of searches people make. Google Trends is provided by Google in the form of relative searches.

Internet search behaviour can serve as an indicator of revealed expectations. People typically search for topics they are curious about or issues that concern them. For example, if someone want to buy bike, they might search for information related to bike, like which bike cost how much? what is the mileage? etc. Similarly, a person worried about rising household expenses and expecting an increase in prices might search for information on inflation. Also, if someone does not want to buy mobile phone, they probably would not search for related information. According to Guzman (2011), a rise in search volumes for the term “inflation” reflects public concern over potential price increases. Therefore, changes in the volume of search queries for inflation can be viewed as a proxy for the public’s expectations about future price movements. Previous studies have demonstrated that Google Trends can help forecast unemployment, private consumption, and food prices across different economies (Choi & Varian, 2012; Vosen & Schmidt, 2011; Seabold & Coppola, 2015).

According to Mostbeck (2019), nowcasting is defined as the real-time prediction of current economic conditions using high-frequency data before official statistics become available, it has emerged as a crucial tool for economic analysis and policy formulation. Nowcasting monthly macroeconomic variables can help address the two challenges, delay in publication and publication in different frequency, faced by the Indian economy. It will also be helpful in tackling other challenges of Indian economy such as complex economic structures and diverse regional variations. It can also support real-time policy decisions. Nowcasted values of macroeconomic variables could make government prepared to economic shocks. Government could respond to these shocks by adjusting policy according to the nowcasted values of macroeconomic variables.

In recent years, the application of machine learning techniques in macroeconomic forecasting has gained significant attention, particularly with the growing availability of alternative and real-time data sources such as Google Trends (Coulombe et.al, 2021; Medeiros et.al, 2021). It provides the timeliness and accuracy of macroeconomic variables forecasts. Traditional models often rely on lagged economic indicators and assume linear relationships; hence they are unable to capture the dynamic nature and non-linear relationship of macroeconomic variables.

In developed economies, nowcasting is primarily focused on refining already robust statistical systems. But India is a developing economy and unlike developed economies nowcasting in

India must address fundamental challenges such as data scarcity, irregular publication schedules, and the need to capture economic activity across formal and informal sectors. According to Agnihotri & Mishra (2021) due to the unavailability of variables and the volatility in the nature of macroeconomic variables, the prediction is harder for developing economies compared to stable and developed nations.

Another challenge in front of policy makers is the structure of Indian economy. It is dominated by informal sector, which is not captured in the official statistics. For instance, domestic workers hired in India are part of the informal economy, which accounts for a huge section of employment in Southeast Asia. Their contribution to the economy is not counted in GDP. Hence, official GDP measures might not be an actual representation of growth. This creates substantial gaps in understanding current economic conditions.

This paper addresses this gap by combining Google Trends data with machine learning techniques to predict four core indicators: unemployment, Consumer Price Index(CPI), real GDP and GDP growth. Using a novel keyword normalization strategy and Woloszko's (2020) two-step modelling framework, we demonstrate that search-based behavioural data can complement official statistics, offering granular, high-frequency insights for real-time policymaking. the following study is divided into six sections. Section 2 contains the literature review, Section 3 deals with data collection, Section 4 covers the research methodology, and Sections 5 and 6 present the results and discussions, and conclusions, respectively.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, Google Trends data have been widely utilized in studies aiming to predict macroeconomic variables. Notably, Choi and Varian (2009a) were among the pioneers who explored the potential of Google Trends for forecasting macroeconomic indicators. The rise of digital footprints, especially online searches, enables real-time economic analysis. Google Trends offers timely, high-frequency, and location-specific search data. Unlike conventional statistics with significant delays, Google Trends reflects public sentiment almost instantly. This makes it useful for nowcasting macroeconomic indicators. Researchers have recognized its ability to provide early signals and complement traditional data sources.

Choi and Varian (2009a) explore the application of Google Trends data for nowcasting economic activity, illustrating how search query information can help estimate home sales, retail sales, automotive sales, and travel trends. In a subsequent study, Choi and Varian (2009b) demonstrate that Google Trends can also be used to forecast initial unemployment insurance claims. Similarly, other authors have also shown that google search data can be used for predicting unemployment, for instance D'Amuri and Marcucci (2010) have forecasted unemployment for US, Suhoy (2008) for Israel, Askitas and Zimmerman (2009) for Germany, Anvik and Gjelstad (2010) for Norway, and D'Amuri (2009) for Italy. Suhoy (2010) have used Google Trends data to nowcast private consumption for Israel. Vosen and Schmidt (2011) forecasted consumption for the US using Google Trends data. This study also shows that Google search query data outperforms survey-based indicators. Kulkarni et al. (2009) applied Google Trends data for predicting housing price, Constant and Zimmermann (2009) have

predicted politics and social trends, Song et al. (2009) have used it in tourism sector and similarly Goel et al. (2010) in entertainment sector.

The application of Google Trends data specifically to the Indian economic context remains limited but promising. Ahani et al. (2021) has demonstrated that Google search data can improve forecasting accuracy for various economic indicators, including unemployment and consumer confidence. The methodology of using search query statistics as economic indicators has shown particular promise during crisis periods when traditional data sources may be less reliable. Some studies which focused on particular macroeconomic variable forecasting are listed below:

2.1 Inflation Forecasting

Google Trends is widely used for inflation nowcasting. Choi & Varian (2009) found that automotive-related searches improve regression models for inflation, benefiting central bank monitoring. Guzmán (2011) created the Google Inflation Search Index (GISI), which can lead actual inflation by up to 12 months, surpassing survey and market measures.

India-focused studies include Samanta (2019), who found that searches for "inflation" and "price" predict CPI-based inflation rates, and Jha & Sahu (2020), who used Google Trends in a Hybrid New Keynesian Phillips Curve model. Their results show that internet-derived inflation expectations enhance forecast accuracy over autoregressive and survey methods. These studies suggest that online inflation expectations are forward-looking, timely, and adaptable.

2.2 Unemployment Nowcasting

Unemployment prediction is another well-explored area. D'Amuri & Marcucci (2012) developed the "Google Index" (GI) using job-search queries, showing it predicts U.S. unemployment better than professional forecasts. Pavlicek & Kristoufek (2015) applied this to the Visegrad countries (the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia), finding strong links between search data and unemployment, especially in the Czech Republic and Hungary.

Search data help capture job-seeking trends in real time, often earlier than labour market statistics, giving policymakers and agencies faster intervention opportunities.

2.3 Tourism Demand Estimation

Siliverstovs & Wochner (2018) used a regional comparison approach with Google Trends to address normalization. Their model, applied to Swiss tourism, yielded accurate demand forecasts, showing that search data can support sectors needing advance planning. Tourism's sensitivity to shocks makes such forecasts valuable for regional management.

2.4 GDP Growth Tracking

Woloszko (2020) created the OECD Weekly Tracker, a neural network model using Google Trends and bias adjustment to estimate GDP growth for 46 countries. This method was especially helpful during the COVID-19 pandemic, when traditional indicators lagged. McLaren and Shanbhogue (2011) also found search data useful for tracking UK labor and

housing markets. Their findings support Google Trends as a timely complement to GDP measurement, especially in volatile times.

While research confirms Google Trends can improve macroeconomic forecasts, most works cover only one or two variables, such as inflation or unemployment, or focus on narrow sectors like tourism. Few try to unify multiple macroeconomic estimates with search data, especially in developing economies.

India has been covered mainly by studies on inflation expectations (Samanta, 2019; Jha & Sahu, 2020) or labour market indicators. No comprehensive monthly nowcasting model using Google Trends covers multiple macroeconomic variables. Given delayed data releases and volatile conditions in India, this gap is significant.

2.5 Research Gap and Objective

Despite broad use, most research focuses on developed economies or single-variable forecasting. There is little study of multi-variable, monthly estimation for emerging markets like India, especially using a consistent approach for inflation, unemployment, Real GDP and GDP growth rate.

The objective of our study is to use Google Trends data for nowcasting monthly macroeconomic variables of India such as unemployment, Consumer Price Index (CPI), Real GDP and GDP growth rate. Our goal is to systematically assess whether this approach provides robust and policy-relevant insights into these key indicators.

In summary, this literature review reveals that the integration of Google Trends data with machine learning techniques represents a promising frontier for macroeconomic nowcasting, particularly in emerging economies like India. While significant methodological advances have been made, substantial opportunities exist for further research, especially in developing country-specific approaches that account for unique economic structures, digital adoption patterns, and linguistic diversity. The potential for enhanced policy responsiveness through improved nowcasting capabilities makes this an area of critical importance for economic research and practice.

3. DATA COLLECTION

3.1 Google Trends Data

According to Guzmán (2011) and Seabold and Coppola (2015), each Google Trends series has two key characteristics. First, the values reported for different time points do not represent absolute search volumes for the selected keywords; rather, they are relative measures. The point of maximum search interest during the selected time frame is assigned a value of 100, and all other values are scaled in proportion to it. Second, the time series representation of a search index for a given keyword and period may vary depending on the date the query is made. This means that even if the reference period remains fixed, the reported data can change over time.

KEYWORD SECTION PROCESS FOR GOOGLE TRENDS DATA

From google trends we have collected the monthly data for the period January 2004 to June 2025, for more than 170 keywords. Keywords were organized into **10 thematic categories**, drawing on existing literature and tailored to the Indian context: -

1. Labour Market & Careers: Inspired by studies such as D'Amuri and Marcucci (2012), which demonstrate that Google search data can serve as a powerful and reliable leading indicator for forecasting unemployment—using keywords like “*jobs*”, “*public jobs*”, “*California jobs*”, “*collect unemployment*”, and “*job center*”—this study draws on similar keyword-based approaches. Likewise, Pavlicek and Kristoufek (2015) examined the relationship between unemployment rates and job-related Google searches for the Visegrad countries, using terms associated with “*job*” and “*work*.” In line with these approaches, we include India-specific keywords such as job near me, temporary jobs, private employment agency, employment news, sarkari job, government jobs, career search, recruitment, developer jobs, waiter, job listings, portfolios, and general job search terms.
2. Housing, Construction & Real Estate: Inspired by McLaren and Shanbhogue 2011, which have explored the potential of using internet search data to nowcast economic activity in the United Kingdom, specifically for the labor and housing markets. The study found a significant correlation between search terms like "JSA" (Jobseeker's Allowance) and ‘unemployment’, ‘unemployment benefit’, ‘unemployed’ and "foreclosure" and terms related to real estate. We have used keywords such as affordable housing, house price index, residential rentals, home improvement, housing bubble, foreclosure, real estate, property, apartments, office space, commercial building, home loan, mortgage, flooring, construction, civil engineering, maintenance, construction consulting, and swimming pools.
3. Inflation & Price Level: Building on studies such as Samanta (year), which examined the usefulness of Google search data for tracking and predicting inflation in India; Guzman (2011), who investigated the potential of Google Trends for forecasting inflation expectations; Jha and Sahu (2020), who incorporated internet search-based inflation expectations into a Keynesian Phillips Curve framework for India; and Choi and Varian (2012), who explored the application of Google Trends in forecasting inflation expectations and consumer sentiment—we include a range of inflation-related keywords in our analysis. These keywords include *Wholesale Price Index (WPI)*, *CPI inflation*, *onion prices*, *petrol price*, *food inflation*, *gold rate today*, *tomato price*, among others, reflecting key items that influence public perception of inflation in the Indian context.
4. Finance and Economic Activity: inspired by the Woloszko (2020) employs Google Trends search data in combination with machine learning algorithms to capture the non-linear relationship between search behavior and GDP growth, using keywords such as “*bankruptcies*”, “*investment*”, and “*luggage*”. we incorporate India-specific keywords including bankruptcy, bankruptcy filings, financial crisis, economic crisis, recession, unemployment, public debt, krach, exportation, business news, economy news, world news, politics, newspapers, economic policy, layoffs.

5. Tourism, Travel & Hospitality: inspired by Siliverstovs and Wochner (2018) investigate the predictive power of Google Trends data for economic activity, using keywords related to tourist destinations such as “*Graubünden*”, “*Zürich*”, and “*Wallis*”. We include search queries on tourist destinations, travel agencies, travel services, cruises and charters, accommodations, spas, timeshares and vacation properties, vacation deals, holiday packages, hotel booking, hotels, flight tickets, luggage, carpooling and ridesharing, rental and taxi services, and general travel-related terms.
6. Retail, Consumer Goods & Lifestyle: Keywords here reflect consumer spending and lifestyle-related searches, including mass merchants and department stores, grocery and food retailers, electronics sale, discount deals, online shopping, book retailers, footwear, accessories, fast food, tobacco products, brands, fashion and style, home and garden, home appliances, beauty services, weddings, birthdays, fitness, health, pharmacy, and veterinarians.
7. Technology, Industry & Business Services: This category merges technology, industrial activity, and professional services, including computer servers, data management, development tools, computer security, CAD and CAM, customer relationship management (CRM), enterprise resource planning, business operations, outsourcing, consulting, corporate, distribution and logistics, printing and publishing, agrochemicals, forestry, food production, manufacturing, dyes, pigments, animal products and services, and agriculture.
8. Transport & Vehicles: Searches in this theme relate to mobility, logistics, and the automotive sector, including car electronics, commercial vehicles, vehicle shopping, vehicle licensing and registration, vehicles in general, trucking, freight, transportation, logistics, package delivery, house moving, aviation, and cars.
9. Arts, Entertainment & Events: Search activity in this group includes acting, theater, performing arts, and events.
10. Miscellaneous Services: This catch-all includes mail, GPS and navigation, and any cross-listed terms like developer jobs.

Each Google Trends series is relative rather than an absolute measure of search volume. The time point with the highest search interest within the selected period is assigned a value of 100, and all other observations are scaled in relation to this peak. As a result, the data do not indicate the actual number of searches, and factors such as changes in internet penetration or variations in Google usage over time do not affect the interpretation of the series. Also, the terms themselves are not independently comparable with each other. But google trends provides us facility to compare the search intensity of up to five keywords. In any batch of five keywords which will be searched using Google trends, the keyword which is searched highest among them will get a value of 100 for that particular time period and rest will receive value related to the highest search for that keyword.

Normalization Strategy

In order to keep the all the keywords’ data relative to only one keyword, so that our overall data could become meaningful, we have used one anchor keyword in every batch of five

keywords. we have used ‘unemployment’ as anchored keyword. So, each batch of data that we have extracted contain ‘unemployment’ and other four different keywords.

The resulting data were stored in more than 45 spreadsheets, each containing four target keywords and one anchor. These spreadsheets were then organized into three groups based on the relative search frequency of the keywords compared with *unemployment*:

Group 1: Similar Scale to “Unemployment”

Keywords with search volumes close to *unemployment*. In this case, *unemployment* was retained as the anchor keyword, allowing the sheets to be merged directly using it as a common reference.

Group 2: Much Lower Search Volume than “Unemployment”

Keywords with significantly lower search intensity. For these, we employed “*tourist destination*”, a medium-volume keyword, as the reference instead of *unemployment*.

Group 3: Much Higher Search Volume than “Unemployment”

Keywords with substantially higher search volumes. For these, “*loan*” was used as the reference keyword.

In addition, two comparison sheets were created:

1. *Unemployment vs. Tourist Destination*
2. *Unemployment vs. Loan*

These comparison sheets enable rescaling across groups, allowing all keywords to be placed on a common scale. Ultimately, *tourist destination* serves as the final reference point, making it possible to integrate all keywords into a single, consistent dataset.

To our knowledge, this represents the most extensive India-specific compilation of Google search activity for macroeconomic forecasting, spanning two decades and incorporating both conventional indicators and uniquely country-specific terms.

3.2 World Bank Data

In addition to Google Trends, we compile annual macroeconomic indicators from the World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI, 2025) for the period 2004–2024. The variables include:

1. **GDP Growth Rate** – Annual percentage change in GDP at constant 2015 USD.
2. **Real GDP** – Aggregate output adjusted for inflation (constant 2015 USD).
3. **Unemployment Rate** – Share of the labor force actively seeking but not engaged in work.
4. **Consumer Price Index (CPI)** – Inflation measure tracking changes in a representative consumption basket.

These indicators provide the macroeconomic benchmarks against which Google search-based measures are evaluated, enabling a systematic comparison between conventional data sources and high-frequency digital indicators.

3.3 Rationale for Combined Dataset

The integration of Google Trends with World Bank data offers both timeliness and credibility. While official macroeconomic indicators such as GDP, CPI, and unemployment are authoritative, they are published with significant lags and limited frequency. By contrast, Google Trends provides high-frequency, real-time information on public search behaviour that can serve as an early signal of economic conditions. Anchoring Google-based measures to established World Bank indicators allows us to test whether search intensity enhances forecasting performance beyond traditional data. This dual-source approach strengthens the robustness of the analysis and contributes to the growing literature on digital indicators in economic forecasting.

4. Research Methodology

This study adopts a two-step forecasting framework inspired by Woloszko (2020), combining machine learning techniques with Google Trends data to predict monthly macroeconomic variables for India.

Step 1: Model Selection Using Annual Data

In the first stage, the monthly Google Trends indicators were aggregated to the annual frequency and merged with official macroeconomic variables obtained from the World Bank. We conducted exploratory analysis to examine the statistical properties of the dataset and performed feature engineering to construct suitable predictors. The dataset was then divided into training and testing subsets using a time-based split to preserve the temporal structure.

Several machine learning models, such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), AdaBoost, Lasso regression, and Support Vector Regression (SVR), were trained and evaluated. Model performance was assessed using mean squared error (MSE) and out-of-sample forecast accuracy. The model with the lowest prediction error was selected as the best-performing specification for the Indian context.

Step 2: Monthly Forecasting Using Google Trends

In the second stage, the selected model was re-estimated using the complete annual dataset and subsequently applied to the high-frequency monthly Google Trends data to generate monthly predictions of macroeconomic variables. To validate the plausibility of these forecasts, we compared the predicted monthly unemployment series against the officially reported annual unemployment data. We conducted Pearson correlation analysis and simple regressions as preliminary checks of consistency, supplemented by robustness tests to examine whether monthly forecasts could meaningfully explain annual variation.

Model Interpretability

To identify the most influential search queries driving the forecasts, we employed SHapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) values. This approach quantifies the marginal contribution of each feature to the model's predictions, thereby enhancing interpretability and linking Google-based behavioural indicators with macroeconomic outcomes. Such interpretability is essential for both academic robustness and policy relevance.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In recent years, the application of machine learning techniques in macroeconomic forecasting has gained significant attention, particularly with the growing availability of alternative and real-time data sources such as Google Trends. Traditional models often rely on lagged economic indicators and assume linear relationships, which may not capture the dynamic and non-linear nature of modern economies.

This section explores the predictive performance of various machine learning models such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, K-Nearest Neighbors, AdaBoost, Lasso Regression, Decision Tree, and Linear Regression, across six key macroeconomic variables: Unemployment Rate, Real GDP, GDP Growth Rate and Consumer Price Index (CPI). Each model is evaluated using three standard error metrics: Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). We have selected that algorithms, which best suited for forecasting each indicator and using it we have predicted monthly values for those macroeconomic variables.

We subsequently analysed the SHAP (SHapley Additive Explanations) values to interpret the machine learning models. SHAP values are grounded in cooperative game theory and provide a consistent way of attributing the contribution of each feature to a model's prediction (Lundberg & Lee, 2017; Shapley, 1953).

Formally, given a machine learning model f and an instance $x \in R^M$ with M features, the Shapley value for feature i is defined as:

$$\phi_i(f, x) = \sum_{s \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|s|! (M - |s| - 1)!}{M!} [f_{s \cup \{i\}}(x_{s \cup \{i\}}) - f_s(x_s)]$$

Where:

- $N = \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ is the set of all features,
- $s \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}$ represents a coalition (subset) of features not including i ,
- $f_s(x_s)$ is the model prediction using only features in subset S ,

The combinatorial coefficient ensures fair weighting across all possible coalitions (Molnar, 2022). Int ossible feature subsets.uitively, $\phi_i(f, x)$ measures the marginal contribution of feature i to the prediction, averaged over all p

The overall model prediction for an observation x can then be decomposed as:

$$f(x) = \phi_0 + \sum_{i=1}^M \phi_i(f, x)$$

Where ϕ_0 is the base value, i.e., the expected prediction across the dataset:

$$\phi_0 = E[f(x)]$$

Thus, the SHAP framework ensures that the prediction is additively explained by the contributions of all features.

In our study, we visualize SHAP values through three complementary plots:

- a. SHAP summary plot, which provides a high-level view of how each feature influences the model's predictions across the entire dataset. The features are listed, ordered by their overall importance on the y-axis. The x-axis represents the SHAP value, which measures the impact (ϕ_i) of a feature on the model's output. A positive SHAP value increases the predicted macroeconomic variable, while a negative value decreases it. The color of each dot in the plot indicates the feature's value for a specific data point. High feature values are represented by red dots, and low feature values are represented by blue dots. This plot reveals the relationship between feature values and the prediction of macroeconomic variables.
- b. Bar chart showing the mean absolute SHAP value for each feature. This provides a more straightforward measure of global feature importance. The x-axis represents the average impact (magnitude) of the feature on the model output, regardless of the direction (positive or negative). This is calculated by taking the average of the absolute SHAP values for each feature across all data points:

$$MeanAbsSHAP(i) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n |\phi_i(f, x^{(j)})|$$

Where n is the number of observations. The features are listed ordered by their mean absolute SHAP value on the y-axis. This plot identifies the top predictors in the model.

- c. SHAP force plot that explains a single prediction. This plot breaks down a specific prediction, showing how each feature contributed to moving the model output from the base value (ϕ_0) to the final predicted value $f(x)$. The base value is the average model output over the entire dataset. This is the starting point for the explanation. The plot represents two coloured bars- red bars, for features with positive SHAP values (which pushes the prediction higher). The length of the bar indicates the magnitude of the impact; and blue bars, for Features with negative SHAP values (which pushes the prediction lower). This plot explains why the model predicted the final prediction value.

These plots collectively enhance the transparency of our models by providing both global interpretability and local interpretability, which is particularly valuable for macroeconomic

forecasting in the Indian context where policymakers require clear explanations of model predictions. we have also analysed the two economic downturn periods, 2008 Global Financial Crisis and Covid-19 pandemic. Prediction and assessment of each series is provided below:

A. Unemployment

We have applied Lasso with alpha value 0.005 for feature selection and results shows that 84 features are suitable for predicting unemployment using machine learning. Figure A.1 presents the performance of different machine learning models in predicting unemployment, evaluated using three commonly employed error metrics: Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). Among the models, Lasso regression stands out as the best performer, achieving the lowest MSE (0.119), MAE (0.297), and RMSE (0.345). This indicates its ability to provide more accurate and consistent predictions compared to other approaches.

Figure A.1: Performance metrics for various machine learning models results on unemployment

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

The K-Neighbors model also performs relatively well, with a notably lower MSE (0.265) and RMSE (0.515), suggesting it can capture non-linear relationships in the data effectively. In contrast, models such as Linear Regression and Gradient Boosting show higher error values, reflecting weaker predictive accuracy in this context. Interestingly, while Random Forest and Decision Tree perform moderately, they do not outperform simpler regularized regression approaches like Lasso.

Overall, the results highlight that regularization-based methods (such as Lasso) are better suited for unemployment prediction in the given dataset, outperforming both ensemble methods and traditional regression models.

Figure A.2: Global Feature Importance (SHAP Summary Plot) for unemployment

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

From the figure A.2, we observe that the ‘*Export Promotion Council*’ emerges as the most influential and volatile factor, with high values consistently driving predictions upward. ‘*Agriculture*’ demonstrates a contrasting pattern, where higher agricultural activity generally reduces predicted unemployment, reinforcing its counter-cyclical role in labor markets. ‘*Gold price*’ also exhibits a pronounced influence, with higher values associated with downward pressure on unemployment predictions. Policy-related factors such as ‘*Union Budget highlights*’ and ‘*Labour card*’, along with employment-related terms like ‘*Layoffs*’ and ‘*Career search*’, show mixed but notable contributions, indicating their relevance in capturing policy signals and labour market dynamics. This global distribution underscores the multifaceted drivers of unemployment predictions and the varying degrees to which feature values alter outcomes across different cases.

Figure A.3: Mean Absolute SHAP Value for unemployment prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

From the figure A.3, we observe that the ‘*Export Promotion Council*’ stands out as the single most influential predictor, followed by ‘*Agriculture*’ and ‘*Gold price*’. These three dominate the feature space, accounting for the largest share of model influence. Secondary but relevant predictors include ‘*Udyam*’, ‘*Rabi crops*’, ‘*Union Budget highlights*’, ‘*Labour card*’, and ‘*Layoffs*’, which play supportive roles in refining forecasts. By contrast, macroeconomic and financial indicators such as ‘*CRR*’, ‘*Sensex*’, ‘*House price index*’, and ‘*Direct tax collection*’ contribute less consistently, suggesting that while they are informative, their predictive strength is relatively weaker. This ranking reinforces the primacy of trade, agriculture, and commodity dynamics as the backbone of unemployment forecasting in the model.

Figure A.4: Single Prediction Explanation for unemployment prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

From figure A.4, we can infer that the ‘*Export Promotion Council*’ shows the strongest upward influence, pushing the predicted unemployment significantly above the baseline expectation. This suggests that trade-related fluctuations captured by export promotion activities are closely tied to localized spikes in unemployment. On the other hand, features such as ‘*Gold price*’, ‘*Union Budget highlights*’, and ‘*Agriculture*’ exert downward pressure, counteracting the prediction to some extent. Additional moderate positive contributions come from ‘*Udyam*’, ‘*Labour card*’, and ‘*Rabi crops*’, which reinforce the forecasted increase. This localized explanation illustrates the model’s reasoning for an above-average unemployment prediction, emphasizing the dominant role of export-related factors while also showing how commodity markets and agricultural indicators mitigate the effect.

Across both local and global perspectives, the analysis consistently identifies ‘*Export Promotion Council*’, ‘*Agriculture*’, and ‘*Gold price*’ as the dominant drivers of unemployment predictions. Export-related activities tend to amplify unemployment forecasts, while agricultural performance and commodity prices provide stabilizing effects. Policy indicators and labour-related terms contribute meaningfully but with moderate influence, reflecting their supplementary role in shaping labour market outcomes. The convergence of evidence from individual predictions, global distributions, and average feature importance strengthens the reliability of these findings. Together, the results demonstrate that machine learning models not only capture predictive accuracy but also offer interpretable insights into the structural and sectoral determinants of unemployment, thereby providing valuable guidance for policymakers

and economic analysts. These insights suggest that policymakers should closely track trade shocks and agricultural cycles, as they play a pivotal role in shaping short-term employment conditions. Early identification of such drivers can enable timely interventions, particularly in export-dependent and rural labor markets.

We then try to see if predicted monthly unemployment and annually published unemployment by world bank have any correlation.

Figure A.5: Predicted monthly unemployment rate compared with officially reported annual unemployment data from the World Bank

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Figure A.5 highlights key dynamics in unemployment trends. The predicted monthly unemployment series shows greater volatility than the yearly data, capturing short-term fluctuations that are averaged out in annual estimates. This volatility is particularly evident during major economic disruptions, such as the Global Financial Crisis (2008) and the COVID-19 shock (2020), where sharp spikes and irregular movements are observed in the monthly predictions.

Despite these fluctuations, the general trajectory of the monthly unemployment series aligns with the yearly World Bank estimates, especially in capturing long-term trends. For instance, the relative stability in unemployment from 2004 to 2015, followed by a gradual decline after 2018, is visible in both series. The impact of COVID-19 is also clearly reflected, with a sharp rise around 2020 before a declining trend in subsequent years.

The figure A.5 illustrates that while annual data provide a smooth representation of unemployment dynamics, monthly estimates offer a richer picture of short-term labour market stress and recovery. This makes the predicted series particularly useful for real-time monitoring and policy assessment, especially during periods of economic crisis where rapid shifts may not be immediately visible in annual data.

Consistent with D'Amuri & Marcucci (2012) and Choi & Varian (2012), search intensity on job-related queries provides strong leading information on unemployment. Our Lasso-based approach achieves competitive predictive accuracy (MSE = 0.119) and high annual alignment (corr = 0.945), comparable to the predictive performance reported in D'Amuri & Marcucci's Google Index for developed-country unemployment forecasts.

B. Real GDP

Applying Lasso with alpha value 0.005 for feature selection, shows that 45 features are suitable for predicting Real GDP using machine learning. We have taken the log values of Real GDP and performed the analysis on it.

Figure B.1: Performance metrics of various machine learning models for predicting real GDP

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

From Figure B.1, it is evident that Gradient Boosting outperforms all other machine learning models, achieving the lowest error values across all three metrics (MSE: 0.0025, MAE: 0.0436, RMSE: 0.0502). This suggests that Gradient Boosting is highly effective in capturing the underlying patterns in Real GDP data, making it the most reliable model in according to the present dataset.

The AdaBoost model also shows strong performance, with relatively low MSE (0.0031) and RMSE (0.0558), followed closely by Decision Tree and Random Forest, which achieve comparable but slightly higher error values. Lasso regression performs moderately well, offering reasonable predictive accuracy but not surpassing the ensemble methods. By contrast, the K-Neighbors model and Linear Regression perform less effectively, yielding higher MSE and RMSE values, indicating weaker predictive ability for GDP forecasting. Overall, the results underscore the superiority of ensemble learning methods, particularly Gradient Boosting, in predicting real GDP, while simpler approaches such as linear regression or distance-based methods provide comparatively less accurate forecasts.

Figure B.2 highlights the dominant role of ‘Labour card’ and ‘PF balance check’ in shaping Real GDP forecasts across the dataset. High values of these features are consistently associated with upward contributions, while low values exert negative pressure, suggesting that formal labour registration and provident fund activity are positively correlated with GDP growth signals. Other features, such as ‘Export Promotion Council’, ‘Union Budget highlights’, ‘Rabi crops’, ‘Mail’, ‘Health’, and ‘Pharmacy’, show smaller but visible impacts, indicating their supportive role in influencing GDP predictions.

Figure B.2: Global Feature Importance for Real GDP prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Additionally, economic activity proxies like ‘*Online shopping*’, ‘*Stock market*’, ‘*Hotel bookings*’, and ‘*Flight tickets*’ contribute modestly, reflecting demand-side signals in the broader economy. Overall, the global distribution indicates that labour-related formalization measures and household financial activities provide the most robust signals for GDP forecasts.

Figure B.3: Mean Absolute SHAP Value for Real GDP prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Figure B.3 also conform ‘Labour card’ and ‘PF balance check’ are the most important features influencing GDP predictions in this model. Their prominence suggests that household-level labour documentation and social security–linked financial activity are highly informative indicators of aggregate economic performance. Secondary contributors include ‘Export Promotion Council’, ‘Mail’, ‘Union Budget highlights’, ‘Rabi crops’, ‘Health’, and ‘Pharmacy’, which, though smaller in magnitude, capture aspects of trade activity, policy communication, agriculture, and healthcare expenditure relevant to GDP dynamics. Demand-driven indicators such as ‘Online shopping’, ‘Stock market’, and ‘Hotel bookings’ rank lower but still provide meaningful, albeit less consistent, contributions.

Figure B.4: Single Prediction Explanation for Real GDP prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Figure B.4 shows that the model’s GDP forecast is slightly below the baseline expectation, with most features exerting negative contributions. The largest downward pull comes from ‘Labour card’, which is -0.09 , and ‘PF balance check’, which is -0.05 , followed by small reductions from ‘Export Promotion Council’, ‘Rabi crops’, ‘Health’, ‘Pharmacy’, ‘loan’, ‘Mail’, and ‘Kharif crops’. No strong positive drivers appear in this case, implying that the forecast is shaped primarily by marginal downward pressures distributed across multiple

indicators. This highlights how institutional and household-level economic indicators can act as localized drags on GDP predictions in specific instances.

Across local and global perspectives, ‘Labour card’ and ‘PF balance check’ emerge as the dominant predictors of GDP forecasts, highlighting the importance of labour formalization and social security–linked household financial activity in explaining output dynamics. Trade and agricultural indicators provide additional signals, while health, pharmaceutical, and consumer demand variables contribute at more moderate levels. Together, these findings suggest that both labour market institutionalization and household-level financial indicators serve as leading signals for GDP fluctuations, complemented by sectoral and demand-driven dynamics. This underscores the utility of interpretable machine learning in uncovering structural drivers of GDP variation and provides a framework for policymakers to monitor household and labour formalization measures as early signals of economic performance.

The dominance of labor formalization and household financial activity as predictors suggests that policymakers should strengthen programs around labor documentation, social security coverage, and trade facilitation. Regular tracking of these indicators can improve early detection of output fluctuations.

Figure B.5: Predicted monthly Real GDP (log values) compared with officially reported annual Real GDP data from the World Bank

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Figure B.5 shows that while the monthly unemployment series closely tracks the annual World Bank estimates over the long run, it also uncovers short-lived fluctuations that are masked in annual data. The result is a consistent expansionary trend punctuated by episodic volatility that aligns with known macro shocks. Around the Global Financial Crisis (2008), the monthly estimates register a discernible softening and higher month-to-month variation, while the annual series moves more gently, evidence that the downturn was real but not prolonged in level terms for this economy. The most dramatic deviation occurs during the COVID-19 shock (2020): the monthly series shows a sharp contraction followed by a swift rebound, whereas the

annual series records only a modest kink. This gap illustrates the value of high-frequency GDP tracking for dating turning points.

Post-2021, the two series reconverge and resume a steady upward trajectory, with monthly fluctuations narrowing relative to the 2017–2020 period, consistent with normalization of activity and policy stabilization. Taken together, the figure shows that the monthly model both validates the annual profile of real GDP and adds information by exposing the timing and amplitude of cyclical swings that annual aggregates obscure, useful for nowcasting and for evaluating policy in real time.

C. GDP Growth rate

Applying Lasso with alpha value 0.005, shows that 106 features are suitable for predicting GDP Growth Rate using machine learning. Figure C.1 shows that among the models, Gradient Boosting delivers the best results, with the lowest MSE (2.225), MAE (1.096), and RMSE (1.492). This indicates that it is more effective at capturing the complex, non-linear dynamics of GDP growth compared to other approaches. AdaBoost and Random Forest also perform relatively well, showing moderate error values and reinforcing the strength of ensemble-based methods in this forecasting task.

Figure C.1: Performance metrics of various machine learning models for predicting GDP Growth rate

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

In contrast, models such as K-Neighbors, Lasso regression, and Decision Tree exhibit higher error levels, suggesting limited ability to handle the variability and fluctuations inherent in GDP growth data. The weakest performance is observed for Linear Regression, with a substantially higher MSE (36.624) and RMSE (6.052), highlighting its inability to capture the underlying patterns in the data.

Overall, the findings suggest that ensemble learning approaches, particularly Gradient Boosting, are the most reliable for predicting GDP growth rates, while traditional linear models perform poorly in this context.

Figure C.2: Global Feature Importance for GDP growth rate prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

According to figure C.2, *Economic slowdown* emerges as the most consistent positive driver of predicted GDP growth, while features like *RBI repo* and *Inflation* frequently push predictions downward. Interestingly, consumer- and sentiment-linked terms such as *Birthday* and *Sports* consistently show up on the positive side, pointing to their association with periods of stronger demand conditions. The heterogeneity in SHAP distributions indicates that the impact of certain features varies across time, with some drivers having episodic but large effects.

From Figure C.3, we observe that when features are ranked by their average importance, *Economic slowdown* stands out as the dominant factor, overshadowing other predictors. This highlights that the model interprets search intensity around slowdown-related terms as a highly reliable signal of shifts in growth dynamics. Other top features include *Birthday*, *Sports*, and *Direct tax collection*, reinforcing the role of consumer behaviour and fiscal policy as central to the model's explanatory power. Traditional variables like *Inflation* and *RBI repo* matter, but their contributions are more modest compared to the unconventional Indicators.

Figure C.3: Mean Absolute SHAP Value for GDP growth rate prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Figure C.4: Single Prediction Explanation for GDP growth rate prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Figure C.4 we observe that the largest positive drivers are *Economic slowdown*, *Direct tax collection*, and *Birthday*, all of which substantially increase the prediction. These results suggest that both macroeconomic concerns (slowdown, tax policy) and behavioural patterns (search intensity around birthdays) carry significant weight in shaping growth expectations. On the other hand, the *RBI repo* rate acts as a mild drag on the prediction, consistent with the contractionary role of monetary tightening.

Taken together, the three figures reveal that the model assigns high importance not just to conventional macroeconomic indicators but also to behavioural and sentiment-driven search patterns. *Economic slowdown* dominates as the single most influential driver, while terms like *Birthday* and *Sports* highlight the predictive power of nontraditional data in capturing shifts in consumption and sentiment. Fiscal policy indicators, particularly *Direct tax collection* and *Income tax slabs*, further complement the model by capturing institutional and policy-related dynamics. Overall, the results suggest that integrating Google Trends with macroeconomic variables enriches the model’s ability to anticipate GDP growth by combining real-time consumer signals with structural policy drivers.

The prominence of search-based sentiment indicators, such as economic slowdown and tax-related terms, underscores the role of behavioural signals in growth monitoring. Incorporating these real-time insights could help policymakers respond faster to shifts in consumption, confidence, and fiscal dynamics.

Figure C.5: Predicted monthly GDP growth rate compared with officially reported annual GDP growth rate data from the World Bank

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Figure C.5 shows that the monthly predictions exhibit substantially greater volatility than the annual series, underscoring the responsiveness of high-frequency estimates to short-term shocks and cyclical fluctuations that are otherwise smoothed out in yearly data.

The Global Financial Crisis (2008) is clearly reflected, with the annual series showing a sharp slowdown to nearly 3%, while the monthly predictions capture more severe contractions and rapid rebounds around the same period. Similarly, the COVID-19 shock (2020) produces a dramatic collapse in the monthly growth series, followed by a sharp rebound, whereas the annual estimates smooth this effect into a deeper but less abrupt trough.

Over the longer horizon, both series broadly move in tandem, reflecting the underlying trajectory of the economy: strong growth in the mid-2000s, deceleration during global and domestic shocks, recovery in the early 2010s, and renewed volatility around 2018–2020. Importantly, the predicted monthly series provides finer granularity, showing turning points earlier than annual estimates, for example, the post-2008 recovery and the rebound after COVID-19.

Overall, the figure demonstrates that while annual GDP growth rates provide a stable long-term perspective, monthly predictions offer valuable insights into the timing, depth, and volatility of growth cycles, making them especially useful for real-time policy monitoring during crises.

D. Consumer Price Index (CPI)

Applying Lasso with alpha value 0.005, shows that 102 features are suitable for predicting CPI using machine learning.

Figure D.1: measurement matrix of different machine learning methods for predicting CPI

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

Figure D.1 reports that among the models, the Decision Tree demonstrates the best predictive accuracy, with the lowest MSE (2.109), MAE (1.252), and RMSE (1.452). Close behind, Gradient Boosting and AdaBoost also achieve strong results, with relatively low error values across all three measures, suggesting that these ensemble and tree-based methods are particularly effective in capturing the dynamics of CPI.

Random Forest performs moderately well but with slightly higher errors compared to Gradient Boosting and Decision Tree. Models such as K-Neighbors and Linear Regression exhibit weaker performance, reflected in higher error values, while Lasso regression performs the poorest, with the largest MSE (21.965) and RMSE (4.687). This indicates that simple

regularized linear methods may not be well-suited for predicting CPI, likely due to the complex and non-linear structure of the data.

Overall, the findings suggest that tree-based methods, particularly Decision Tree and Gradient Boosting, provide the most reliable forecasts of CPI.

Figure D.2: Global Feature Importance for CPI prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

From figure D.2 we observe that the 'RBI repo rate' consistently showed a strong negative relationship, whereas 'Kharif crops' generally exerted a positive impact. Interestingly, features such as 'Flooring', 'Newspapers', 'Transportation', and 'MSME' demonstrated both positive and negative influences depending on the observation, highlighting the heterogeneous effects of these factors on CPI dynamics.

Figure D.3: Mean Absolute SHAP Value for CPI prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

From figure D.3 we can infer that the 'RBI repo' and 'Kharif crops' stand out as the most influential variables, dominating the model's decision-making process. Secondary factors such as 'Flooring', 'Newspapers', 'Enterprise Resource Planning', and 'Transportation' also play a role, though with smaller relative importance. This ranking allows us to identify which economic and financial indicators the machine learning model considers most relevant for CPI forecasting.

Figure D.4: Single Prediction Explanation for CPI prediction

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

From figure D.4 we observe that the 'RBI repo' exerted the strongest negative influence on the prediction, lowering the model's output significantly. 'Kharif crops' added positively to the forecast, pushing the predicted CPI upward. Other variables, such as 'Flooring', 'Recruitment', and 'Enterprise Resource Planning', had smaller but still noticeable effects.

Taken together, the analysis reveals that the keyword 'RBI repo' plays a central role in shaping CPI outcomes, with consistent downward pressure on inflation predictions. Whereas keyword 'Kharif crops' tend to push inflation upward. Other indicators, while less dominant, contribute to refining the forecasts in different contexts. These SHAP analysis enhances trust in our machine learning models.

The results emphasize that monetary policy measures and agricultural production patterns remain critical drivers of inflation expectations. Close tracking of these signals, especially during supply-side disruptions, can help fine-tune inflation management strategies

Figure D.5: Predicted monthly CPI values compared with officially reported annual CPI data from the World Bank

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

From figure D.5 we observe that the predicted monthly series have substantial volatility, reflecting short-term fluctuations in inflationary pressures, while the annual series smooths out these variations, providing a clearer picture of long-term inflation trends.

During the Global Financial Crisis (2008), the annual CPI continued to rise, peaking around 2010 at close to 12%, capturing the inflationary impact of global commodity price shocks. The monthly predictions, however, display sharper short-term spikes and dips, showing how price volatility intensified during this period. Similarly, during the COVID-19 shock (2020), the monthly CPI series captures erratic price movements driven by supply disruptions and demand shocks, whereas the yearly CPI reflects a more gradual increase and subsequent moderation.

Results align with Guzmán (2011) and Choi & Varian (2012) which show internet search indices contain inflation signal; however, our CPI nowcasts achieve only moderate explanatory power relative to annual series ($R^2 \approx 0.55$), reflecting India-specific volatility in food/supply shocks that search intensity imperfectly captures.

5.1 Model Validation and Scope

To evaluate the reliability of the machine learning–based nowcasting framework, we compared the yearly averages of predicted monthly macroeconomic indicators with official World Bank statistics for 2004–2025. Two complementary validation approaches were employed:

- Correlation analysis to assess the strength of association between predicted and actual series.
- Simple OLS regression to evaluate explanatory power, using official statistics as the dependent variable and predicted values as regressors.

Table 1 summarizes the pairwise correlations between the predicted yearly averages and official data. Predictions for unemployment (0.94) and real GDP (0.94) show exceptionally high correlations, suggesting the models capture the underlying trends effectively. CPI also demonstrates a strong relationship (0.74), while GDP growth rate (0.67) shows moderate alignment, reflecting the difficulty of capturing short-term price and growth dynamics.

Table 1: Correlation between the yearly average of predicted macroeconomic variable and official yearly world bank data

Indicator	Correlation
GDP Growth Rate	0.6677
CPI	0.7419
Real GDP	0.9362
Unemployment	0.9448

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

We further tested the alignment between predicted and official values using simple linear regressions. Table 2 presents the R^2 values and coefficients. The explanatory power is highest for unemployment ($R^2 = 0.893$) and real GDP ($R^2 = 0.877$), confirming the robustness of predictions for these variables. CPI and GDP growth rate achieve moderate R^2 values (0.55 and 0.45, respectively). In most cases, the estimated slope coefficients are statistically significant and close to one, further validating the predictive framework.

Table 2: Regression between the yearly average of predicted macroeconomic variable and official yearly world bank data

Indicator	Regression R^2	constant	Predicted indicator
GDP Growth Rate	0.446	2.5303	0.5534
CPI	0.550	1.2150*	0.7417
Real GDP	0.877	2.2660	0.8169
Unemployment	0.893	1.0669	0.8261

Note: * indicates insignificance at 5% level.

Source: Computed by authors using Google Trends data

These results confirm that the framework performs exceptionally well for stock variables such as unemployment and real GDP, where predictions closely track official trends and capture long-run dynamics. In contrast, GDP growth rate poses greater modelling challenges due to its higher volatility and sensitivity to short-term shocks. CPI forecasts lie between these extremes, reflecting both structural and cyclical influences.

Despite these challenges, the predicted monthly series offer valuable additional insights, especially in times of crisis. They not only mirror official yearly data but also reveal turning points earlier, as demonstrated during the 2008 global financial crisis and COVID-19 pandemic, when the models captured sharp contractions and rapid recoveries that were smoothed in annual estimates. This highlights the potential of search-based behavioural data for early warning systems and real-time policy assessment.

From a scope perspective, this work provides a proof of concept for integrating high-frequency internet search data into macroeconomic forecasting frameworks in emerging economies. The methodology is scalable: it can be extended to state-level indicators, additional high-frequency datasets, and refined ensemble approaches to improve accuracy for inflation and growth measures. By leveraging behavioural signals from search patterns, policymakers can

complement traditional statistics with a cost-effective, near real-time decision-support tool that enhances responsiveness to economic shocks.

6. CONCLUSION

Overall, the results highlight the effectiveness of combining Google Trends data with machine learning techniques to generate timely, high-frequency estimates of key macroeconomic indicators for India. The findings show that no single algorithm dominates across all variables; instead, model selection must be indicator-specific, with Gradient Boosting, Decision Trees, and Lasso excelling in different contexts. SHAP analysis provides transparency, revealing that search intensity captures meaningful economic signals, from trade activity and agricultural output to monetary policy and consumer sentiment, offering a richer understanding of underlying drivers. Comparisons with official World Bank data confirm strong alignment for stock variables such as real GDP and unemployment, while capturing the short-term volatility and turning points that annual statistics obscure. Importantly, the framework demonstrates its value during periods of economic stress, accurately reflecting the dynamics of the 2008 global financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic. Together, these results provide compelling evidence that search-based behavioural data can complement traditional economic indicators, offering a powerful tool for real-time monitoring and early policy intervention in a data-scarce, rapidly evolving economic environment.

We compare our forecasting performance with the leading literature on search-based nowcasting. Prior work has shown Google Trends can predict unemployment and inflation signals in developed economies (D'Amuri & Marcucci, 2012; Choi & Varian, 2012; Guzmán, 2011), and recent efforts have extended search-based GDP trackers to multiple countries (Woloszko, 2020; Bouayad et al., 2022). Consistent with these studies, we find that search intensity contains strong signals for stock-like series: unemployment (best model Lasso; test MSE = 0.119; corr = 0.945) and real GDP (best: Gradient Boosting; corr = 0.936) show high alignment with annual series. In contrast, flow measures such as GDP growth is harder to nowcast ($R^2 \approx 0.45$), reflecting volatility driven by short-lived commodity and supply shocks that search-data alone may not capture. Overall, our results corroborate and extend the literature by demonstrating that, for India, Google Trends combined with ensemble learning produces timely and interpretable nowcasts for core macro aggregates, while cautioning against overreliance on search data for highly volatile price measures.

Despite the promising results of this study, several methodological limitations must be acknowledged. First, Google Trends data are inherently volatile and subject to sampling variability due to Google's undisclosed data sampling and normalization procedures. This results in fluctuations in search indices for identical queries conducted at different times, posing challenges to reproducibility and reliability. Although the use of anchor keywords helps mitigate batch normalization issues, more robust statistical adjustments and multiple data samplings would enhance the stability of the input features. Second, zero values in Google Trends data may not always indicate an absence of searches but could reflect low search volumes below Google's reporting threshold, which introduces potential missing data bias and may obscure meaningful signals. Third, the relative nature of Google Trends measures means that absolute search volumes and changes in internet penetration or access across different

demographic groups are not fully captured, which may limit the generalizability and representativeness of the findings, particularly in emerging markets with uneven digital access such as India. Fourth, while machine learning models provide flexible and powerful tools for nowcasting, they carry risks of overfitting and limited interpretability, which require rigorous validation techniques such as cross-validation and careful interpretation to avoid overstatement of causal relationships. Lastly, the lack of integration with additional high-frequency data sources or survey-based controls constrains the explanatory power of the models, suggesting avenues for future research to build more comprehensive and representative forecasting frameworks.

Future research could integrate search data with other high-frequency indicators such as mobility, payments, or satellite data to build more comprehensive real-time forecasting frameworks. Such efforts would further strengthen the role of digital trace data in economic surveillance and policy design.

DECLARATION

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to check the grammar of the sentences. After using this ChatGPT, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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